

Storytelling Method as a Media for Forming Character in Early Children in Timbong Village, Banggai Tengah District, Banggai Laut District, Central Sulawesi Province

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ABSTRACT

This service was carried out in Timbong village, specifically Timbong Kindergarten, with approximately 30 students divided into two classes, namely class A and class B. The process of storytelling or reading this book is carried out before the learning process begins and also when learning has been completed. The teacher reads in front of the class, and then the students listen. After reading fairy tales or stories, the teacher will give students the opportunity to ask questions. And at that time, the teacher will instill character by conveying the character values contained in the story

INTRODUCTION

Early childhood education is one form of education that focuses on laying the foundations for physical growth and development (gross and fine motor coordination), intelligence (thinking power, creativity, emotional intelligence, and spiritual intelligence), socioemotional (attitude, behavior, and religion), language, and communication, according to the stages children go through. Every aspect of a child's development must receive encouragement or assistance that can help the child achieve his level of development at that age. Apart from that, early childhood is a brilliant time to do things and provide education.

Character education itself is an educational process aimed at developing values, attitudes, and behaviors that exude noble morals or noble character. So character education is considered very important to be instilled in children from an early age. Through this character education, early childhood children are prepared to improve the quality of implementation and educational outcomes in schools, which leads to the formation of student character and noble morals in a complete, integrated manner, balanced, and in accordance with graduate competency standards.

Every child is born with their own potential, this potential is in the form of hereditary factors and habituation factors. Therefore, every child needs stimulation in the golden period of a child's life, namely the toddler years. Various groups assess that the Indonesian nation is currently in a critical condition that requires appropriate treatment. This is happening because, currently, there is a decline in morals that requires character education at the educational level. It is hoped that through character education, which is implemented from an early age, it will be possible to instill good character values in children so that children can grow into human beings who have good character, are responsible, and have devotion to God Almighty.

It is hoped that character education in schools can be one way to overcome social problems that arise at this time. Every human being needs education so that he can live a good life. One of the things that is needed at this time is character education. Character education is very important because it really helps people have good moral values so that they can be well accepted by society. Character education must be introduced and instilled at an early age so that in the future, children will have good character or personality so that they can shape themselves into dignified and devout human beings.

Fairy tales are useful for instilling positive characters in young children. According to Samani, Muchlas, and Hariyanto (2013), the aim of character education is to instill values in students and renew the order of life together, which is directed at respecting individual freedom and improving the quality of education in schools, which leads to achieving the formation of students' character and morals in a complete and balanced manner in accordance with graduate competency standards.

Character education is very important in the world of education. According to Huck (1993), Hepler (2004), and Arkoboesono (2007), a fairy tale is a narrative or story in written or oral form that has been around for generations.

Meanwhile, according to Tina Kogh's opinion in (Anggraeni & Rafiyanti, 2022), a fairy tale is a story that has been used in a civilized manner for a long time as a communication tool in which there is an event or events, the characters of the story, or messages taken from the characters in the story. Based on the opinions of the experts above, it can be concluded that a fairy tale is a story, both oral and written, that has been around for a long time, with fairy tales being used as a communication tool to instill good character, which can be taken from the message contained in a story. Fairy tales can help children recognize their surroundings.

Fairy tales are divided into several groups. According to Imam Ralibi in Khan (2020), fairy tales can be divided into two categories: storytelling using props (story books, hand puppets, etc) and storytelling without using tools, namely telling stories without using tools and only using facial expressions and voice innotations that try to imitate real voices. Early childhood education is a form of education implementation that focuses on laying the foundations for physical growth and development (gross and fine motor coordination), intelligence, social emotionality, language, and communication according to the stages that children go through early age.

Character education is an educational process aimed at developing values, attitudes, and behaviors that exude noble morals or character. So character education is considered very important to instill in children from an early age. Character education is one of the soft skills, namely guidance for students to become complete human beings with character in the dimensions of heart, mind, and body, as well as feelings and intentions. Character education is carried out through formal, informal, and nonformal education on the formal education route. So the most basic education is preschool, so formal character education starts from here. Beautiful stories will enter the soul and form beautiful characters. Storytelling is very important to give to children both at home and at school because, through fairy tales, teachers or parents can provide learning to children in a fun way while making them feel entertained.

Apart from that, there are also several benefits of storytelling, namely that it can increase children's intelligence because every child can imagine, increase intelligence, strengthen relationships, instill love, have moral messages, and gain new knowledge as a means of instilling character in children. Storytelling is a natural cultural practice and is best taught from an early age. Storytelling or telling a story about something can be done in many ways to make the story more interesting and lively, for example, with sound animation through technology applications or the help of traditional props.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Fairy tales as a medium for telling stories or as a medium for cultivating character in early childhood can be done by providing a story that contains moral messages and the final conclusion of a fairy tale that children can apply in their daily lives, able to instill and also grow character within themselves. a child. (Noor, 2011) states that storytelling or storytelling activities are a means of fostering close relationships between parents and children. Apart from that,

storytelling activities can also be an opportunity to increase children's knowledge as well as train children's thinking abilities. Storytelling activities can be carried out with kindergarten or elementary school children and their parents.

METHODOLOGY

This activity was carried out at the Timbong Village Kindergarten School with approximately 20 students, consisting of 2 classes, namely Kindergarten and Kindergarten B. This activity was carried out before learning started or before entering the main discussion, and it was also carried out when the students were going home. The fairy tales chosen are fairy tales that contain meaning and character content, which are then improvised with supporting sentences by the teller of the story.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

During the activity, we focused on the attitude of helping and responsibility that exists in early childhood, which was seen on the second day when researchers made direct observations of children's behavior. The first day was precisely February 7, 2023. During break time, we asked the children to clean up the messy toys in the classroom, and there were only a few children who cleaned up the toys, and the others just watched. Not only that, on the second day we also tested whether there is a responsible character in children at PAUD Permata Bunda in Timbong Village, namely by telling them to put in their writing utensils after finishing lessons by themselves without the help of their parents. It turns out that all children can or are able to do it themselves.

After seeing some of the good and not so good behavior and character of children, on the third day, February 8, 2023, we tried to tell a fairy tale that contained moral values and character for children. fairy tale about "Bebe the arrogant grasshopper". This story tells about, "Bebe, an arrogant grasshopper, who never stops mocking his friends. He considers himself the strongest and perfect. Jepi the giraffe and Rara the turtle are two of Bebe's friends who are often teased and looked down upon by him".

When they heard the fairy tales, the children looked bored, but after we used supporting media such as fairy tale books or stories and pictures of animals, all the children started to pay attention and listen to them. The fairy tale contains moral values and characters about people who should not be arrogant. This is then conveyed as a conclusion from the fairy tale, which is taken advantage of. When conveying conclusions, use influential sentences, for example, "children must not be arrogant, not greedy, not nosy, be for giving, humble, and always obey their parents' advice".

Observations continued on February 9, 2023. At the beginning of the first hour of the meeting, we repeated the fairy tale that had been told yesterday, then asked the children a little about the content of the fairy tale. The children had a good response, they still remembered the contents

of the fairy tale that was told. Then, after break time, before starting the lesson, the researchers tested again by asking the children to help clean up the messy toys in the classroom. A good response from children was seen in cleaning up messy toys. This can be concluded by encouraging children to foster a spirit of mutual help that has been successfully developed within the child, as long as the child is accustomed to doing and emulating good things.

In observations carried out on February 10, 2023, researchers wanted to test the fairy tale "Dino the Generous Heart". In the plot of the fairy tale, it tells the story of Dino, a good and diligent goat, in a village where he only has an orchard. In the garden, various trees grow, such as mango trees, bananas, guavas, and elephant grass. Dino was diligent in taking care of him so that the trees in his garden grew well. This attracted the attention of the neighbors in the village, including Monik Simonet and Kuma Dikuda. Kuma and Monik visit the dino garden every day. Dino felt happy because his neighbors visited him. The fruit season has passed, and the trees in Dino's garden no longer bear fruit. At the same time, Dino fell ill. He can no longer care for his garden properly. Meanwhile, Monik, who likes picking bananas and mangoes, is never seen. Kuma, who likes to eat elephant grass and guava, is no longer visible. Luckily, Karbi came to visit Dino. So, he was the one who looked for medicine and took care of Dino. At home, Dino is being cared for by Karbi. Karbi, who was often ridiculed by Monik and Kuma, turned out to be kind". From inside, they heard Monik and Kuma's conversation. "Come on, let's look for fruit elsewhere!" said Monik. "Come on! Anywhere else would definitely taste better than in this garden!" Kuma answered. "Yes, besides, I'm afraid of contracting the disease. Dino just got sick, right?" "Come on, quickly. I also don't want to catch dino disease. Hi, scary!" Kuma shouted as he ran. Dino became even sadder when he heard that. Monik and Kuma only come when the garden bears fruit. As soon as the garden does not bear fruit.

The researcher then conveyed to the children the conclusion of the fairy tale. We must continue to be generous to friends even though we are being taken advantage of by them, and we must be kind to everyone even though they are not seen favorably by those people, just like the goat. Today we also immediately tested children's generous nature again to see whether it had an impact on children's behavior. At lunch time, we tried to get children to share food with each other, and immediately they shared the food they had with their friends.

A little generous value is to continue to be kind to friends and to get them used to developing a generous attitude from an early age. The last day of research was on February 11, 2023. We repeated the test about the character of being generous and not arrogant towards children. Like at the beginning of the meeting, it turned out that after observing and repeating again, they were willing to help put away toys and be kind enough to share food with their friends. Children should not be arrogant, and children also want to put the stationery they have used back into their

respective bags and arrange their shoes in the shoe box. It is through the medium of fairy tales that we can experience the benefits that can be gained from cultivating character and instilling noble character in children. Apart from that, children are also taught to adopt positive values or wisdom contained in the content of a fairy tale. Through telling stories, children not only get pleasure, but they also get a more meaningful and broader education. It can even touch on aspects of forming a child's personality when they are growing up.

They are given knowledge and explain children's characters through fairy tales in a pleasant and peaceful atmosphere. The material provided is about storytelling. Which is in their environment and becomes their property or daily habit. Storytelling is not just stories about myths or the like, but also real events that are packaged in such a way with the help of technology that they are interesting and rich in moral messages. Stories that contain values that conflict with morals and humanism may have the content or storyline changed according to local cultural norms or religious values. The output of this activity tends to shape the child's personality or character for the better and indirectly introduces local culture as an invaluable asset.

Therefore, it is not enough for a child's character to be built or carved through the packaging of beautiful stories or tales in the cognitive domain, it also needs to be built in an integrated manner in the affective and psychomotor domains. In the sense that children "know" (cognitive) the characters of the characters in the stories or tales being told, children "feel" (affective) the behavior of the characters played by the characters and the results of the actions or roles of the story characters. After conducting research observations, researchers can conclude that children's characters can be developed through fairy tales. The children responded well after the researchers told a fairy tale that contained the character values of being generous and not being arrogant.

One of the benefits of the storytelling method is that it can shape children's characters. After being given treatment, the child's character becomes good. Through the storytelling method, the child can directly grasp the moral message, which can make the child want to imitate or emulate the characters in the story. Just by watching and listening to stories in storybooks, children can imagine looking directly at pictures that exemplify good characters.

The benefits of stories for young children are:

1. Developing inner contact between children, teachers, and parents
2. Media for conveying messages to children
3. Education of children's imagination or fantasy
4. Can train children's emotions or feelings
5. It helps the self-identification process
6. Enriches the inner experience
7. Can be used as entertainment or to attract children's attention. Can shape a child's character

In storytelling, there will be a process of value transformation through the behavior and character of the characters in the story. Moreover, when storytelling is assisted by media and technology, the storytelling atmosphere becomes lively and interesting, and social communication occurs between children and teachers or parents. Telling fairy tales and stories to children must be done correctly in order to form good character in children. Pay attention to the reasoning and logic of the story by choosing the correct words and sentences, because at that time you are "carving" or "sculpting" the child's character. Therefore, educators and parents must be able to clearly differentiate between imaginative delivery and realistic stories.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the results of the discussion above, it is clear that the storytelling method is an effective method for instilling character values in students. However, it should be noted that reading stories or fairy tales requires special skills so that they are interesting and the message you want to convey is absorbed or can leave an impression on the students' hearts.

FURTHER RESEARCH

This research still has limitations so further research needs to be done on this topic "Storytelling Method as a Media for Forming Character in Early Children in Timbong Village, Banggai Tengah District, Banggai Laut District, Central Sulawesi Province".

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